

**PHARMACOGNOSTICAL AND PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS OF
GUDUCHI-MUSTADI KWATHA (YAVAKUTA)- AN AYURVEDIC
HERBAL FORMULATION FOR VANDHYATVA (FEMALE
INFERTILITY) DUE TO ANOVULATORY FACTOR ASSOCIATED
WITH OBESITY**

Alifeeya Vaghela^{*1}, Shilpa B. Donga², Harisha C. R.³

^{*1}PG Scholar, Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stree Roga.

²Prof. & H.O.D., Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stree Roga.

³Pharmacognosy Laboratory, Institute of Teaching and Research in Ayurveda (ITRA), Opp. B Division Police Station, near Reliance Mall, Gurudwara Road, Jamnagar, Gujarat, India-361008.

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***Corresponding Author**

Alifeeya Vaghela

PG Scholar, Department of Prasuti
Tantra Evam Stree Roga.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Infertility is a widespread problem affecting individuals, families, and communities. Obesity has a well-established association with impaired reproductive function, with rising BMI linked to higher rates of menstrual irregularities and anovulation. Obese women show altered neuro-regulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis, leading to disturbed ovulation and reduced fertility. Since anovulation accounts for about 40% of female infertility, a significant proportion is directly or indirectly related to obesity, along with lifestyle, medical, and environmental factors. Here, *Guduchi-Mustadi Kashaya* is mentioned by Acharya Charaka as a drug for the management of *Atisthaulya* was selected for the management of obesity. So, for initialization of standardization and assurance of the quality of herbal compounds, pharmacognostical and pharmaceutical analysis

should be done. **Methods:** *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* was subjected to microscopic evaluation for pharmacognostical and physicochemical analysis, such as loss on drying, total

ash, water soluble extract, alcohol soluble extract and pH value. **Results:** Pharmacognostical study showed the presence of certain identifying characters of all the ingredients of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* like *Guduchi*, *Musta* and *Triphala*. As per the preliminary physicochemical analysis, loss on drying percentage of the *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* was 8.58% w/w, pH value was 6, total ash value was 3.67 % w/w, water soluble extractive was 41.91%w/w and methanol soluble extractive was 42.57%w/w. **Conclusions:** Pharmacognostical and physico-chemical observations revealed the specific characteristics of all active constituents of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* confirmed the purity and genuineness of the drug.

KEYWORDS: *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta*, *Atisthaulya*, Pharmacognosy, Pharmaceutical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Infertility affects millions of people and has an impact on their families and communities. The relationship between obesity and reproductive functions has been known for many years.^[1,2] and it is still being explored.^[3] With increasing Body Mass Index (BMI), it was possible to observe that the percentage of oligomenorrhea increased from 18% to 32%, amenorrhea increased from 2% to 13% and the total percentage of anovulation increased from 32% to 55%.^[4] According to American Society for Reproductive Medicine (ASRM), obesity is the cause of fertility struggles in 6% of women who have never been pregnant before.^[5] Overweight and obesity have been considered a worldwide epidemic, and in many parts of the world, they now represent the greatest threat to public health. In obese, there is an alteration in neuro-regulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis.^[6] These alterations may impair ovulatory function and also reproductive health. The most common overall cause of female infertility is the failure to ovulate, which occurs in 40% of women with infertility issues.^[7] It is postulated that a significant proportion of these cases are either directly or indirectly related to obesity. Factors such as faulty dietary habits, increasing weight, smoking, medical conditions, environmental pollutants, medications, family medical history and infections might affect couple's conception.

In the current scenario, obesity (*Sthaulya*) has a significant impact on infertility. It involves excessive accumulation of *Medo Dhatu* due to irregular dietary habits and a sedentary lifestyle, leading to nourishment of only *Medo Dhatu* while other *Dhatus* remain deprived. As per Acharya Sushruta, *Sthaulya* is a *Rasanimitaja Vikara*, and since *Artava* is an *Upadhatu* of

Rasa Dhatu, its function is also impaired, resulting in anovulation and menstrual irregularities. In the management of *Atisthaulya* Acharya Charaka mentioned the use of *Guduchi*, *Musta* and *Triphala*,^[8] *Guduchi* and *Musta*, which balance *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha*. These properties help reduce fat and excessive moistness, the main factors in *Sthaulya*, by enhancing digestive fire at the tissue level, digesting free radicals, and promoting *Medohara* action. *Triphala* further supports this by improving digestive fire, reducing *Kapha-Meda*, and enhancing scrapping, thereby breaking the pathogenesis of *Sthaulya*.

Safe and effective herbal medicines require proper identification, purity, and standardization, which becomes difficult in powdered or dried forms. Pharmacognostical and physicochemical studies help in authenticating plant materials, detecting adulterants, and ensuring quality. In Ayurveda, timely quality assessment of raw and finished drugs is essential to maintain efficacy and credibility. Hence, the present study aims to establish the pharmacognostical and phytochemical profile of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* to ensure its authenticity and standardization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection, identification and authentication of raw drugs.

The raw materials were procured from the pharmacy of ITRA Jamnagar, and the raw drugs were identified and authenticated in the pharmacognosy laboratory of Institute of Teaching and Research in Ayurveda, Ministry of Ayush, Govt. of India, Jamnagar. The ingredients and parts used in *Guduchi-Mustadi Yavakuta* are given in Table 1.

Table No. 1: Ingredients of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwathayavakuta*.

Sr. no.	Drug Name	Botanical name	Family	Part Used	Proportion
1	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.)	Menispermaceae	Stem	1 Part
2	<i>Musta</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> Linn.	Cyperaceae	Root	1 Part
3	<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Emblica officinalis</i> Linn.	Euphorbiaceae	Fruit Pericarp	1 Part
4	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Combretaceae	Fruit Pericarp	1 Part
5	<i>Bibhitaki</i>	<i>Terminalia belirica</i> Roxb.	Combretaceae	Fruit Pericarp	1 Part

METHOD OF PREPARATION OF GUDUCHI-MUSTADI KWATHA YAVAKUTA

The coarse powder of *Guduchi*, *Musta* and *Triphala* were prepared in the pharmacy, ITRA, Jamnagar. These were stored under aseptic and good hygienic conditions. All drugs were

taken in equal proportion and made into *Yavakuta* form. This coarse powder was provided to patients in a sachet with written instructions in the vernacular language.

PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STUDY

The pharmacognostical study was divided in to organoleptic study and microscopic study of the finished product.

Organoleptic study: The genuineness of the polyherbal formulation can be found with organoleptic characters of the given sample. Organoleptic parameters comprise of colour, odour, taste and touch of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* which was scientifically studied.

Microscopic study: *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* ingredients was taken in powder form and dissolved with water and microscopy of the sample was done without stain and after staining with phloroglucinol and HCl. Microphotographs of all ingredients *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* were also taken under Corl-zeisstrinocular microscope.^[8]

Physico-chemical analysis: With the help of various standard physico-chemical parameters, *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* was analysed. The common parameters mentioned for *Yavakuta* in Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India and CCRAS guidelines are loss on drying, total ash, water soluble extract, alcohol soluble extract and pH value.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

The initial purpose of the study was to confirm the authenticity of the drugs used in the preparation of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta*. For this, all ingredients were subjected to organoleptic and microscopic evaluations to confirm the genuineness of all the raw drugs. Later, after the preparation of formulation, pharmacognostical evaluation was carried out. Organoleptic evaluation of organoleptic features like colour, odour and taste of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* were recorded and are placed in Table 2.

Table No 2: Organoleptic Characters of *Guduchi-Mustadikwathayavakuta*.

Parameter	Result
Colour	Brownish
Odour	Characteristic & Bitter
Taste	Bitter
Touch	Rough course powder

Microscopic evaluation: Microscopic evaluation was conducted by dissolving the ingredients of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* in the distilled water and was studied under microscope for the presence of characteristics of ingredient drugs. The diagnostic characters of *Guduchi* are Simple starch grains (Figure 1), the diagnostic characters of *Musta* are Annular vessels (Figure 2 A), Lignified fibres (Figure 2 B) Parenchyma cells with starch grains (Figure 2 C), the diagnostic characters of *Amalaki* are Group of fibres (Figure 3 A), Silica crystals (Figure 3 B), the diagnostic characters of *Haritaki* are Epicarp cells (Figure 4 A), Stone cells (Figure 4 B) and the diagnostic characters of *Bibhitaki* are Trichomes (Figure 5 A), Stone cells & sclereids (Figure 5 B), Rosette crystals & Brownish coloured matter (Figure 5 C), Pitted sclereids (Figure 5 D).

Physico-chemical parameters: Physico-chemical parameters like Loss on drying, total ash value, water soluble extract, alcohol soluble extract and pH value were found within the normal range. Details are shown in Table 3.

Table No 3: Physico-Chemical Parameters Of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta*.

S.N.	Parameters	<i>Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta</i>
1	Loss on drying %(w/w)	8.58
2	Total Ash value %(w/w)	3.67
3	Water soluble extract %(w/w)	41.91
4	Alcohol soluble extract %(w/w)	42.57
5	pH (by pH meter) at room temp	6

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

DISCUSSION

The present study was undertaken to standardize and authenticate *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha* (*Yavakuta*) through pharmacognostical and physico-chemical evaluation, as quality assurance is essential for Ayurvedic formulations used in complex conditions like *Vandhyatva* due to

anovulatory factor associated with obesity. The findings help in establishing the identity, purity, and consistency of the formulation as per classical and scientific standards.

Organoleptic evaluation revealed a brownish colour, characteristic odour, bitter taste, and rough coarse texture, which are in accordance with the inherent properties of the constituent drugs. Microscopic examination showed distinct diagnostic features of *Guduchi*, *Musta*, *Amalaki*, *Haritaki*, and *Bibhitaki*, confirming the genuineness of all ingredients and absence of adulteration in the finished product.

Physico-chemical parameters such as loss on drying, total ash value, water- and alcohol-soluble extractives, and pH were found within normal limits as per Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia guidelines. These results indicate good quality, stability, and extractive potential of the formulation, supporting its traditional use and providing scientific validation for *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* in the management of obesity-associated anovulatory infertility.

CONCLUSIONS

Pharmacognostical and physico-chemical observations revealed the specific characteristics of all active constituents of *Guduchi-Mustadi Kwatha Yavakuta* confirmed the purity and genuineness of the drug.

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